

Formal Verification of Risk-Aware Trading Strategies Using Markov Decision Processes and Probabilistic Model Checking

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Abstract

Automated stock trading systems operate in highly dynamic and uncertain financial markets, where failures can lead to significant financial losses. Traditional backtesting approaches evaluate trading strategies only on a limited set of historical scenarios and cannot exhaustively analyze all possible market behaviors. Formal verification provides a mathematically rigorous alternative by modeling trading decisions as Markov Decision Processes (MDPs), enabling the verification of probabilistic safety and performance properties. However, applying formal verification to multi-asset portfolios introduces the well-known state-space explosion problem, as the number of possible portfolio configurations grows exponentially with the number of assets.

This study presents a scalable framework for the formal verification of multi-asset stock trading strategies using mathematical abstraction and symbolic model checking. Initial experiments showed that explicit-state verification was feasible for small portfolios but exhausted available memory when extended to six stocks. To address this limitation, a novel abstraction layer was introduced within the portfolio valuation logic, replacing explicit tracking of individual asset-price permutations with an aggregated representation of joint market behavior. Combined with symmetric asset templates and module renaming, this abstraction enabled the construction of portfolio models containing up to 50 assets.

The proposed framework was implemented in the PRISM model checker and verified using symbolic Multi-Terminal Binary Decision Diagrams (MTBDDs), which exploit structural regularities within the model to achieve substantial memory compression. Experimental results demonstrate successful verification of portfolios with up to 3 billion reachable states while computing precise probabilistic and reward-based properties expressed in Probabilistic Computation Tree Logic (PCTL). The work shows that mathematical abstraction and symbolic verification can effectively overcome scalability barriers in formal financial modeling, enabling rigorous analysis of large-scale algorithmic trading strategies.